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Preparing Technicians for the 4th Industrial Revolution

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ABSTRACT

The fourth industrial revolution is rapidly and drastically changing work in the tech sector. This requires tech workers to embody new competencies. So far, previous research efforts resulted in competency sets that were insufficiently capable at addressing the new requirements tech works should meet. Therefore, we conducted two scientific studies to specify these. In the first study, semi-structured interviews (n=54) were conducted involving CEOs and HR directors from tech companies. Based on these data, we found five major technological developments and their implications for tech workers' jobs. In the second study, we asked the same CEOs and HR directors to indicate which competences they expect to be the most important for tech workers in line with the five technological developments. This resulted in a questionnaire that was handed to a larger sample of tech companies' CEOs and HR directors (n=236).

Our research shows that the fourth industrial revolution will fundamentally change the work activities and job complexity of tech workers. Different technological developments in automation, optics, and big data start interacting with each other, reinforcing their impact on the tech workers' jobs. According to respondents, this requires a tech worker with an outstanding and up-to-date knowledge base regarding his profession, as well as the ability and mind-set to closely collaborate with tech

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workers from other professions. Our practical implications reveal how Engineering Education, tech companies, and their tech workers can collectively establish these new requirements, helping tech workers to become and remain futureproof.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fourth industrial revolution, also known as ‘Smart Manufacturing’ (Kang et al., 2016), ‘Industrie 4.0 (BRD)”, and ‘Smart Industry’ (NL), can be described as the digitization of the (high-)tech industry and focusses on the merger of three technological developments (Smart Industry, 2017). Firstly, new production technologies emerge, such as 3D printing and robotics. These are expected to further automate the production process. Secondly, in addition to the production technologies, information and sensor technology develop rapidly and become more intuitive too. For instance, technologies regarding big data and the internet of things increasingly digitize the management of production process and enable machines to make autonomous decisions. Thirdly, technology creates room for new business concepts as it increasingly integrates people with each other. Resulting in shorter supply chains and shifts from product-oriented business models towards service-oriented business models (servitization).

Different from previous industrial revolutions, ignited by discoveries such as the steam engine and computer technology, the fourth industrial revolution is believed to be accompanied by an impact and the pace of change mankind has not encountered yet. Where previous industrial revolutions were concentrated on one major technological breakthrough, the fourth industry comes with a combination three radical developments. This combination of new, powerful and flexible technologies, combined with cheap data storage, strong analytical software, fast internet-of-things technology, and innovative business models, generate fruitful opportunities for new developments to emerge, such as: virtual reality, complex production process simulations, and autonomous production machinery. The increasing pace of change has to do with both as the life cycle for technological innovations will shorten and urge for a faster time-to-market. Meaning that new technologies will enter the market faster than ever before and come with a broader and more disruptive, rather than an incremental, character.

It is anything but surprising that these predications on the fourth industrial revolution launched various research agendas devoted the impact of technological developments on the future of work. However, most of these research efforts were focused on the question which jobs will disappear due to an increasing use of technology (Went, Kremer, & Knotternerus, 2015; Frey & Osborne, 2017). By exclusively focussing on these disappearing jobs, researches have overlooked an important question, namely how these technological developments impact the actual work activities of employees. This question does merit much more attention than it currently receives (e.g. Ras et al., 2017). Because, as recent studies showcase, new technologies are expected to make work more complex and require a highly-skilled workforce that is capable of designing, implementing and using innovative technologies in their daily operations (Usanov & Chivot, 2013). Furthermore, businesses are discovering new ways of organizing as a result of these technological developments and are working towards new business models, leading to a demand for new skills and competences too.

These new work demands are expected to lead to a growing urge for new competencies: a total of required knowledge, skills, and attitudes. These are often described as '21st century skills', 'lifelong competences' or 'key skills' (Voogt & Roblin, 2012). To illustrate, as a result of aforementioned technological developments, employees should be capable of: (1) working closely together with the newest technology; (2) having the ability to manage one's personal development and proactively respond to organizational change; (3) coping with constantly changing work demands due to an increasing customization of products and services. In order to cope with these developments, and remain employable, employees should master competencies focussed on adaptability and multidisciplinary collaboration (Van Est & Kool, 2015). Despite the strong line of research regarding employees' future competencies, these publications often include vague descriptions of the actual knowledge, skills, and abilities required.

Before addressing this paper's aim, we would like to underline why it is necessary to focus this paper on the tech sector. Of course, one could argue that technological developments will have an impact on all sectors. However, we do have serious reasons to believe that work and competency requirements in the tech sector will dramatically change on a relatively short term. This could be ascribed to the technologies' decreasing purchase prices and rising amount of applications. Providing large companies new, sophisticated solutions and, more important, lowering the financial burden for small and medium-sized tech companies to acquire these technologies as well. This already results in situations where parts of tech workers' jobs are being robotized, smart software are used to micro manage the product streams, and new steps are made towards fully automated, customer-driven production lines (lights out factory or smart factory).

Furthermore, some tech companies already allow customers to operate their manufacturing technology over the internet, enabling same-day delivery of orders. In such fully automated systems, there is hardly any need for operator intervention. The tech workers that still work there are now in constant contact with the customer. They help customers through the (digital) production process, translate customer demands into final production, understand machine planning, have an excellent grasp of the supply chain, and are apt at using methods of data analysis. Goos (2013) infers that such innovative ways of organizing will go hand in hand with developments such as self-managing teams, staff rotation, and ongoing training of competences, like co-operation and information sharing.

In line with the highlighted knowledge gaps and dynamics in the tech sector, the goal of this paper is to specify how technological developments are affecting the tech workers' jobs (study 1) and what this means for the competencies they should master to cope with these (study 2). Filling the knowledge gaps would result in a valuable contribution to Engineering Educational programmes as these studies' findings provide the yardstick on how to futureproof tech workers, both students and those working on the factory floor, for working in tomorrow's tech sector.

2 STUDY 1: HOW DOES WORK IN THE TECH SECTOR CHANGE DUE TO RECENT TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENTS?

2.1 Methodology

In order to thoroughly understand and describe how technological developments will change work in the tech sector, a qualitative research approach was taken. 54 semi structured interviews were conducted involving Dutch tech companies' CEOs and HR directors. In total, 141 CEOs/HR directors of 141 companies were approached, resulting in an 38% response rate. Twenty respondents were from larger companies (employing >250 employees) operating in the high-tech industry. The remaining respondents (N=34) were from small (<50 employees) and medium-sized enterprises active in the following sectors: installation, mechatronics, construction, electronics, and IT. Companies were selected based on their work floor technology. We included companies that were praised for their technological innovations or used the newest technologies on a daily base. These selection criteria were used for two reasons. Firstly, we assumed that these interviewees would be well-informed about the current technical status quo and, therefore, best capable of predicting future developments. Secondly, by selecting technology-driven companies, we expected more room for practical examples during the interviews. These would help us to better frame and understand the interviewees' predictions.

During the semi-structured interviews, respondents were asked to describe the technological developments they expect to have an impact on work in their tech company for the upcoming five to ten years. The semi structured character of the interviews allowed the researchers to ask the respondents to clarify their pictured technological developments, increasing both our understanding and the validity of results. By clarifying these developments with examples, respondents were challenged to describe the impact of technological developments on work in the (high-)tech sector as precisely as possible. Additionally, the respondents were also asked to describe how future work in the tech sector will differ from their current jobs.

The interviews were translated into verbatim transcripts. These were imported into the Atlast.ti coding program and inductively coded by two independent researchers. In order to increase the results' validity, inter-rater reliability was established as both researchers compared their coding structures to agree upon the final codes to use. Next, four researchers used the final codes to determine how technological developments change work in the tech sector. Through a group discussion, the researchers agreed upon five overarching developments that would clarify how the future of work in the tech sector is being influenced by technological developments.

2.2 Results

Based on the analysed interview data and coding process, five developments were found that shed light on how the future of work in the tech sector will be influenced by technological developments. These findings exceed the boundaries of the tech workers' workplace as the interviewees mentioned how the business, as a whole, will be affected by the newest technologies too. In this paper, the term 'tech worker' will be used in its broadest sense to refer to all technical employees (high and low educated) working in the tech sector.

Development 1: Tech jobs will become more diverse and demanding. The integration of smart software, big data, smart machinery, and robotics means that a tech worker's job will become more diverse and demanding. We found three explanations. First, the fast-growing increase in 'customized' products, services, and innovations require the tech workers to rethink their job on a daily, or even an hourly, base. In order to properly do this, tech workers should be capable of: rapidly and effortlessly switching between different work demands, deploying a variety of knowledge and skills, and coping with constantly changing customer demands. Second, in order to stay competitive, tech workers should work closely together with highly-complex robots and systems (e.g., programming, tooling, fixing errors). This will increase the tech workers' job complexity as most respondents did not perceive these technologies as user-friendly. However, most of the respondents reported a weak trend regarding the simplification of user interface design and the introduction of helpful tools (e.g., tables or augmented reality). These should make the complex technologies easier to use and, thus, mitigate the accompanied job complexity. Third, the tech workers' constant development will become increasingly important for two reasons. On the one hand, tech workers should remain capable at using the newest technologies. These are expected to be introduced at a higher speed than accustomed to, especially for tech workers in SMEs. On the other hand, tech workers should have the required competencies for coping with situations that, due the technological acceleration and mass-customization, become unpredictable and unstructured. These three explanations come with an important practical implication according to the respondents: approximately half of the respondents claim that tech jobs require employees with a higher level of education. In contrast to the other half of the companies, who state that more intense, long-term, and company-specific educational programs and workplace learning should prepare tech workers for future job demands.

Development 2: Team dynamics and work places will face radical change. Technological developments are expected to drastically impact the tech workers' team composition and work environment. More specific, tech workers working in teams that involve colleagues, customers, and suppliers, is expected to become the norm. Respondents provided two explanations for this. First, advanced systems and smart machines will integrate the processes that run throughout the value chain with each other. This brings those involved in the value chain, from first to end tier, closer together and fosters intense, direct collaboration. Second, respondents expect an increase in the demand for Just-In-Time customization. This requires effective, short-cycled projects where members from various departments (e.g., product development, finance) and the value chain work closely together to timely deliver. These projects are expected to affect the tech workers' work place as they will spend an increasing amount of time at other departments, companies, and online (e.g., virtual teams).

Development 3: Work will become increasingly automated and robotized. Respondents from larger companies stated that robots and automation tools are already taking over simple, routine tasks from their tech workers. A scenario almost half of the SME respondents expect to happen soon. They predict that prices for robotics and automation tools will lower due to an increasing competition among suppliers and economies of scale benefits. Lowering the financial burden for SMEs to purchase these technologies. Additionally, the expectations and demands from business-to-business partners and suppliers are expected to reinforce the automation and robotization of the SME work floor. Next to the routine tasks, respondents from both company sizes expect robotics and automation tools to take over more complex

routine tasks and even non-routine tasks as these technologies are becoming: more advanced, highly interconnected with each other, self-learning and -correcting, flexible, and, on the long term, easy to (re)program. Requiring tech workers to transition from manual labour to: programming, analysing large amounts of system data, checking machine statuses, fixing errors, and optimizing production processes, products, and services.

Development 4: The use of augmented and virtual reality will intensify. Virtual and augmented reality systems and accompanied cloud-techniques are expected to provide various efficiency benefits to both larger companies and SMEs. By receiving augmented reality work instruction from distant machine builders, tech companies are being enabled to build and maintain their own machines and quickly resolve errors themselves. Virtual reality could be used for step by step training of tech workers and help them when executing advanced work activities. In addition, respondents from larger companies expect that they will soon be capable of using virtual reality to simulate process designs (digital twinning) and, based on the analysis of the simulations, generate opportunities for radical process optimizations, at a fraction of the costs involved in building a real production line.

Development 5: New product-market combinations will demand for adaptive tech companies. According to the larger companies, technological developments will lead to new product-market combinations, unexplored business models, and different ways of organizing. One of these developments point towards the fully automated factory where customers login on the machines, operate them, and receive their customized product the same day. Another would be the turnaround from traditional production towards service provision (so called servitization), which is being sparked by leveraging large amounts of (machine) data in a smart way. Both developments demand for the tech companies' organizational adaptability. Implying that tech workers should be better capable at functioning in switching teams that can timely and autonomously respond to such market developments.

3 STUDY 2: WHAT DO THESE CHANGES IN WORK MEAN FOR THE REQUIRED COMPETENCES OF TECH WORKERS?

3.1 Methodology

Based on the outcomes of study 1, the same tech companies' CEOs and HR practitioners were asked to provide a description of the new knowledge, skills and attitudes tech workers should possess for successfully coping with the five technological developments. We did this through different types of interviews. The first ten interviews had an open character. We asked tech companies to describe for each of the five technological developments what competencies tech workers should possess to properly cope with these for the upcoming five years. In order to thoroughly understand these competencies, we asked respondents what they meant with their competencies and asked for practical examples. The remaining 44 interviews were conducted in a semi-structured manner. We asked these respondents to determine whether the competencies found in open interviews were applicable for their tech workers too. When considered applicable, we asked the respondents to illustrate this through practical examples. At the end of these interviews, we provided respondents the possibility to list new, unmentioned competencies and elaborate on these.

The transcripts of the interviews were imported into the Atlas.ti software program and were coded by three independent researchers. The three coding structures were compared with each other and, through discussion, agreement was found on the final codes. These provided us with an overview of knowledge, skills and attitudes that tech workers should master. Subsequently, we converted these codes into a questionnaire. The items were based on the themes that were found in final codes. We tested our questionnaire through four additional interviews with tech companies' CEOs and HR practitioners. The questionnaire was tested for overall clarity and item formulation. These interviews resulted in various linguistic changes, making the questionnaire easier to understand and complete.

In total, the questionnaire captured twelve competencies: three knowledge aspects (expert knowledge, multidisciplinary knowledge and business knowledge), six skill aspects (adaptability, commercial skills, accuracy, analytical skills, communication skills and collaboration), and three attitude aspects (proactivity, creativity / innovation and dealing with uncertainty). We shared the questionnaire with 331 tech employers'. The response was 72%: 236 employers completed the questionnaire. Among these companies, 91 were small companies (<50 employees), 113 medium-sized companies (50 to 250 employees) and 32 large companies (250+ employees). A wide range of companies in the tech sector has been included: from metal and electrical companies to more high-tech process technology and ICT companies. Appendix A captures an overview of the competencies and related questions. For each competency, respondents were asked how important these are for future tech workers to possess (five-point Likert scale: 1 = very unimportant; 5 = very important). As the technological developments from study 1 were expected to become a reality within five to ten years, we used a five-year time frame for the questionnaire.

The scales from the questionnaire were tested for reliability, using Cronbach's Alpha with a test criterion of $\alpha > .70$. Based on this criterion, four questions were omitted from the data analysis for the following competences: business knowledge, creativity/innovation, commercial skills, and adaptability. Table 1 provides an overview of the number of questions, after omission, per competence and the associated reliability. Despite the insufficient reliability for the creativity/innovation competency ($\alpha = .68$), the decision has been made to include the competency as the test criterion of $\alpha > .70$ was almost met. For each competency, we aggregated the underlying scores and analyzed its importance compared to other competencies. We did this by comparing the average scores between competencies and looking for significant differences, using independent sample T-tests. Additionally, we use the same statistical test for comparing the average scores within each company size. We did this as we wanted to know if company size placed a different emphasis on certain competencies. For instance, larger companies could be interested in rather specialist competencies, while small and medium-sized companies might place more emphasis on generalist competencies. As each company size comes with its distinct agenda and available resources, or the lack of it, we have not looked at the differences between companies.

Table 1. Overview Cronbach's Alpha after omission

Domain	Competencies of the tech worker of the future	Number of questions	α
Knowledge	Expert knowledge	6	.91
	Multidisciplinary knowledge	4	.76
	Business knowledge	4	.70
Skills	Analytical skills	5	.83
	Accuracy	6	.72
	Communication skills	6	.74
	Collaboration	5	.90
	Creativity/Innovation	5	.68
	Commercial skills	4	.78
	Proactivity	3	.78
Attitude	Dealing with uncertainty	4	.72
	Adaptability	4	.77

3.2 Results

Based on the findings represented in table 2, we found all tech companies agreed that business knowledge and expert knowledge are the most important knowledge-related competencies for their future tech workers to master. They considered these competencies significantly more important than multidisciplinary knowledge. It is notable that this finding applies to all companies, regardless of the size. However, by looking, per company size, at the amount of significant differences between high- and lower-ranked competencies, we found that small-sized companies placed most emphasis on business knowledge. While other company sizes did this for both business knowledge and expert knowledge.

Accuracy and creativity/innovation were found to be most important skill-related competences. However, in this domain, we found that each company size placed a different emphasis on the skill-related competencies. To illustrate this, we found that large organizations considered collaboration, accuracy, and creativity/innovation most important. Which differs in comparison to, small companies, which underlined the importance of accuracy, creativity/innovation, and collaboration, and medium-sized companies emphasized accuracy, creativity/innovation, and commercial skills. Again, by looking at the significant differences per company size, we found that larger companies require their tech workers of the future to master more skill-related competencies, compared to the smaller and medium-sized companies.

When looking at the attitude domain, we discovered that the companies consider adaptability to be the most important attitude-related competency, followed by a proactivity and dealing with uncertainty. Comparable to the previous domain, differences between company sizes are visible. For tech workers in larger companies, dealing with uncertainty was considered key. While other company sizes underlined the absolute importance of adaptability. For this domain, the significant differences per company size reveal that large companies address more attitude-related competencies to their tech workers of the future, compared to the other companies.

Table 2. Comparison of Importance Scores for the Competencies

Domain	Competencies of the tech worker of the future ¹	Total Importance (N=236) ¹	Small companies (<50) (N=91) ³	Medium-sized companies (<250) (N=113) ³	Large companies (>250) (N=32) ³
Knowledge	Expert knowledge	3.97 ^b	3.86 ^y	4.02 ^x	4,10 ^x
	Multidisciplinary knowledge	3.50 ^c	3.50 ^z	3.43 ^y	3,73 ^y
	Business knowledge	4.11 ^a	4.14 ^x	4.07 ^x	4,11 ^x
Skills	Analytical skills	3.48 ^b	3.44 ^{yz}	3.41 ^y	3.88 ^{xy}
	Accuracy	3.83 ^a	3.86 ^x	3.77 ^x	4.00 ^{xy}
	Communication skills	3.45 ^b	3.35 ^z	3.49 ^y	3.66 ^y
	Collaboration	3.55 ^b	3.47 ^{yz}	3.48 ^y	4.04 ^x
	Creativity/innovation	3.76 ^a	3.68 ^{xy}	3.79 ^x	3.91 ^{xy}
	Commercial skills	3.50 ^b	3.41 ^{yz}	3.63 ^{xy}	3.27 ^z
Attitude	Proactivity	3.62 ^b	3.63 ^{xy}	3,53 ^y	3,93 ^x
	Dealing with uncertainty	3.49 ^c	3.47 ^y	3,37 ^z	4,01 ^x
	Adaptability	3.86 ^a	3.75 ^x	3,93 ^x	3,92 ^x

1 – Appendix B contains the descriptions of the competencies of the tech worker of the future

2 - all averages within the same domain (Knowledge, Skills, or Attitude) and having different superscripts (a, b, c) indicate statistical difference ($p < .05$).

3 – all averages within the same domain (Knowledge, Skills, or Attitude), same company size (Small, Medium-sized, or Large), and having different superscripts (x, y, z) indicate statistical difference ($p < .05$). Differences between company sizes have not been administered.

4 BUILDING BRIDGES: LEARNING COMMUNITIES AND SKILLS LABS

The effects of technology on work that companies describe are innovative compared to the discussion about the effects of automation on work as it has been going on for several decades (see, for example, Scheele, 1999). It is about a difference in both the nature and the degree of change. As far as the nature is concerned, it has already been pointed out that various technical changes come together at the same time and combine with cheap data storage, strong analysis software and fast internet technology. This makes developments possible that were previously impossible, such as virtual reality, complex production process simulation and autonomous production machines or vehicles. The extent of the change is mainly due to the speed of change and the penetration of the new technology. The speed of technological developments in the fourth industrial revolution is greater than ever before, the impact is wider, and the changes are also more disruptive. According to the companies, this is because technologies such as smart machines, big data and sensor technology have now developed to a level that is applicable and affordable for many more, even smaller companies. As soon as a company responds to technological developments, the consequences for those lagging behind are often so large and radical that the pioneering initiator removes all its market threat. In addition, the technologies are merging into new concepts such as "smart factories" and highly advanced (software) systems that transcend individual business boundaries. According to companies, this amalgamation also ensures that technology penetrates quickly and massively within all domains a company. According to them, this leads to adjustments in (production) processes, ways of organizing or even in revenue models, and as a result the work and the working environments of tech workers are changing drastically and quickly.

If we examine the competencies that are needed in the new industrial reality, a picture quickly arises, one that presents employers looking for a five-legged sheep; tech workers who have excellent professional knowledge, are capable of work well-together and have a proactive attitude. This demand has been the case for year several years now. Furthermore, with regard to knowledge aspects, it was noticeable that the tech companies are fairly clear about the increasing importance of expert knowledge: a "broad" education is not enough. According to the tech companies, it is essential that a tech worker is socially competent, can collaborate and negotiate with employees, customers or suppliers from other disciplines or ones with a different background. In addition, respondents emphasized the increasing importance of new knowledge areas such as sensor technology, robotics and nano technology.

Regarding the skill aspects, it was noticeable that a large number of respondents, certainly in the large companies, made it clear that the boundaries between a tech worker and a business administrator are blurring. A tech worker in these companies will increasingly have to possess a far-reaching insight into the processes, the supply chain and business models. One must be able to continuously place the work or project in relation to the company or even the entire chain and must be actively involved with internal and external developments. They also see the ideal tech worker as a kind of marketer; someone who can make connections between people quickly, knows how to sell themselves and has a keen eye for new opportunities. Concerning skills aspects, tech companies mainly emphasize the flexibility and development capacity of employees. They find it difficult to put those aspects into practice, while at the same time they often have an acute need to further develop that capacity among their tech worker. It is striking that aspects related to creativity and innovation were mentioned less, while it is generally expected that these are precisely the aspects with which an employee can survive in the rapidly changing labor market (Meel, 2015).

However, relating back to our earlier description, the tech worker of the future is not a five-legged sheep. Tech employers realize that the tech worker of the future cannot have all the competencies if they start their career. A distinction can be made between "*qualifiers*"; skills that everyone must possess in order to function in the new industrial reality and "*order winners*"; skills that distinguish a tech worker on the labor market. The following can be identified as *qualifiers*: (1) being an expert in one's own field and (2) constantly looking for new knowledge. Concluding that current and in-depth knowledge is still the essential characteristic for a tech worker: a broad education is not enough. Order winners on the other hand can be referred to as: (1) business knowledge (understanding having an overview of what is going on in the company and then acting) and (2) renewing by collaborating with other disciplines and thereby renewing their own knowledge and convert them into practical applications for the organization.

Respondents see Engineering Education and companies playing an essential role in training tech workers for the future. Companies emphasize that they want to contribute to the training of tech workers, in particular, the areas of business knowledge, communication and commercial skills and collaboration. However, the basic dimensions of work in the new industrial reality, and the competencies that result from it, require more than vocational training. Instead, it demands tech companies who train their tech workers at the workplace. To assure (young) tech workers have the ability to cope with new technological developments, being able to function in

unstructured and unpredictable situations and being able to work with new teams, Engineering Education and the business community will have to work together to a greater extent. The competencies that emerge from this research require not only a training program and work content that challenges the learning of the necessary competences, but a permanent development path that tech workers thoroughly, with long-term focus and step-by-step can transform for the ever-changing, unpredictable and unstructured work environments. Welten (2013) describes this as training in smart missiles: "people who can adapt at lightning speed because they are able to change course completely, and that requires that they forget what they had originally learned".

It is not only up to tech companies to facilitate this, but also up to Engineering Education. Engineering Education will have to build learning environments that prepare tech workers for the technological developments described in this paper. From that perspective, the various Dutch, regional partnerships between Engineering Educational Institutions, business and government that are currently being built in the form of "field labs", "learning communities" and "skills labs" are promising. Within these initiatives, a practice-oriented learning environment is being built, full of modern technology that is being introduced by companies. These environments offer tech companies, students and Engineering Education the opportunity to work together in a powerful way to develop the skills of the tech worker of the future.

We have developed a first concrete guide for training the tech workers of the future with five companies in the Smart Industry. Via mooc.saxion.nl students, employers and employees have access to five publicly accessible practical cases with which tech workers learn what the most important technological developments are and what that means for their work and the competencies required for this.

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APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRE TECH WORKER OF THE FUTURE

Questionnaire: Competencies for the tech workers of the future

The tech worker of the future ...

Expert Knowledge (in his/her own field)

- 1 ... is constantly looking for new knowledge within his/her field of expertise.
- 2 ... has in-depth knowledge within his/her field of expertise.
- 3 ... is an expert in his/her own field.

Multidisciplinary knowledge

- 1 ... is a generalist: has broad knowledge about various disciplines.
- 2 ... has knowledge of related fields of expertise of fellow technical colleagues.
- 3 ... has knowledge of the market and its customers.
- 4 ... has knowledge of the disciplines that he/she closely cooperates with.

Business knowledge

- 1 ... understands the impact of work on the profitability of the company
- 2 ... understands how his/her work contributes to the product being made.
- 3 ... knows what to do in the event of a change or error in the process.
- 4 ... knows all the steps within the production process.

Analytical skills

- 1 ... is able to interpret complex information and convert this into concrete behaviour.
- 2 ... is able to discover and recognise connections in information and / or data streams.
- 3 ... is able to solve problems in a structured manner and distinguishes between main and minor issues.
- 4 ... is able to understand the essence of customers' demands and can act accordingly.
- 5 ... is able to translate complex information and/or data streams into manageable steps.

Accuracy

- 1 ... constantly examines the quality of his/her own results.
- 2 ... seeks feedback from others on the quality of his/her own work.
- 3 ... strictly adheres to working instructions and procedures.
- 4 ... is meticulous in every act he/she performs.

5 ... realises the importance of accuracy in his/her actions and the consequences of errors.

6 ... continuously examines and challenges the quality of the results delivered by others.

Communication skills

1 ... communicates easily with different levels.

2 ... is able to empathize with others when transferring discipline-specific knowledge.

3 ... is able to accurately express his/her opinion.

4 ... is adept at communicating with others in the organization.

5 ... is able to maintain contacts with customers and support them in an approachable manner.

6 ... is able to provide the customer with technical details in an understandable manner.

Collaboration

1 ... provides input to the work of other professional disciplines.

2 ... works closely together with other disciplines towards a common goal or result.

3 ... solves complex problems in collaboration with other disciplines.

4 ... supports colleagues in their work.

5 ... is open to criticism and questions when cooperating with colleagues.

Creativity and innovation

1 ... thinks out-of-the-box and goes beyond the existing framework.

2 ... sees errors as learning opportunities and focuses on solutions.

3 ... explores and broadens the limits of the technical possibilities.

4 ... deliberates and reflects about how products can be improved.

5 ... designs innovative products together with the customer.

Commercial skills

1 ... advises customers on purchasing products.

2 ... negotiates and convinces customers about buying products.

3 ... understands the needs and wishes of the customer and can adjust products accordingly.

4... considers the customer perspective and customer experience in order to better understand the customer needs.

Pro-activity

- 1 ...is able to expresses his/her opinion within the group.
- 2 ...is constantly seeking opportunities and takes the initiative to seize all within reach.
- 3 ... takes initiative to search for improvements for products and works to execute these.

Dealing with uncertainty

- 1 ... handles conflicts of interests well.
- 2 ... continues to function optimally regardless of tight deadlines.
- 3 ... manages the constant update of products and/or work procedures smoothly.
- 4 ... handles changing expectations well.

Adaptability

- 1 ... easily switches between different working environments
- 2 ... adjusts easily to changing team configuration.
- 3 ... switches quickly and often between work and machine work.
- 4 ... adjusts easily to setbacks and/or resistance.

APPENDIX B: DESCRIPTIONS OF THE COMPETENCIES OF THE TECH WORKER OF THE FUTRUE

Competencies of the tech worker of the future Tech Worker	Description
Expert knowledge	Expert in own field, in-depth knowledge, constantly looking for new knowledge
Multidisciplinary knowledge	Broad knowledge, knowledge of adjacent areas, multidisciplinary knowledge
Business knowledge	Understands and works in line with the production process, and understands the impact of work on profitability.
Analytical skills	Interprets complex information, sees through relationships, solves structured problems, brings out essence of customer wishes
Accuracy	Continuously questions quality, acts in accordance with work rules and process, is precise.
Communication skills	Communicates easily with other levels, makes easy contact, can maintain contacts with customers
Collaboration	Can work with other disciples and solve problems. Supports colleagues.
Creativity/innovation	Thinking out of the box, broadens the boundaries of technical possibilities, can improve products
Commercial skills	Advises and convinces customers, can adapt products to customer needs
Proactivity	Voices own opinion, takes initiative, continuously seeks opportunities, takes action towards own development
Dealing with uncertainty	Can cope with conflicting interests and tight deadlines. Is able to switch quickly between changing expectations.
Adaptability	Adapts easily in the event of a setback or resistance, and can switch quickly and often between activities